

Potentiometric Studies on the Complexes of Some Trivalent Metal Ions with N-(2-Hydroxy-5-Phenylbenzylidene) 2,4-Dimethylaniline

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal complexes of Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} with N-(2-hydroxy-5-phenylbenzylidene) 2,4-dimethylaniline. The formation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the dissociation constants of its metal complexes have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength 0.1 M in 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxane-water medium. The order of stability constants of the chelates is found to be $Pr^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Sm^{3+}$.

FROM the literature available on the determination of stability constants it is seen that no work on the solution stability constants of N-(2-hydroxy-5-phenylbenzylidene) 2,4-dimethylaniline and its metal complexes has been reported so far.

The present investigation is aimed to determine the stability constants of Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} complexes with N-(2-hydroxy-5-phenylbenzylidene) 2,4-dimethylaniline.

Experimental

The ligand N-(2-hydroxy-5-phenylbenzylidene) 2,4-dimethylaniline was synthesised by refluxing equimolar quantities of 4-hydroxy-3-aldehydo-biphenyl and 2,4-dimethylaniline in alcohol. The crude product obtained was repeatedly crystallised to obtain an analytically pure sample (observed m.p. 130°). The purity of the sample was tested by elemental analysis.

Found : C, 83.64 ; H, 6.31 ; N, 4.63%,

Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{19}NO$; C, 83.7 ; H, 6.31 ; N, 4.65%.

Calvin-Bjerrum's technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹ was used to determine the dissociation constants of the reagent and formation constants of its metal complexes at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in 75 : 25 v/v dioxane-water medium.

pH measurements were carried out on Corning model 12 precision research pH meter. The meter provides a full scale expansion of any pH unit over a range of 0 to 14 with an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit on the expanded scale, when two point calibration is used. During the titrations, oxygen free nitrogen presaturated with solvent mixture was bubbled through the solution. The solutions of the metal perchlorates were prepared using metal carbonates or oxides of A. R. grade. All these were titrated complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (1.04 M) solution.

- (i) 5 ml of (0.16 M) $HClO_4$ + 5 ml of (0.64 M) $NaClO_4$ + a requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxane.
- (ii) 5 ml of (0.64 M) $NaClO_4$ + 5 ml of metal perchlorate (0.008 M) in (0.16 M) $HClO_4$ + the requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxane.
- (iii) 5 ml of (0.64 M) $NaClO_4$ + 5 ml of metal perchlorate (0.008 M) in (0.16 M) $HClO_4$ + requisite amount of reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution plus 30 ml of dioxane.

Results and Discussion

The values of $\bar{n}_A$ at corrected pH values as determined by the method of Irving and Mahnot³ were compiled from the titration data using solutions (i) and (ii). Calculations of proton-ligand stability constants were carried out by plotting a graph of $\bar{n}_A$ against pH which extended over a range of 0.277-1.972 in $\bar{n}_A$ scale (Fig. 1). The pK_1 and pK_2 values corresponding to $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and $\bar{n}_A=1.5$ respectively were obtained from the curve. The plots of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ and $\log(2-\bar{n}_A/\bar{n}_A-1)$ vs pH were also drawn and from the former pK_1 was evaluated and from the latter pK_2 was evaluated. The values agree quite well with those obtained by half-integral method.

From the titration curves using solutions (ii) and (iii) $\bar{n}$ (average number of ligand molecules attached

Fig. 1. Formation curve of N-(2-hydroxy-5-phenylbenzylidene) 2,4-dimethylaniline.

per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponent) values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria (Fig. 2). From these formation curves the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were determined. The plots of $\log (\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ and $\log (2-\bar{n}/\bar{n}-1)$ vs pH were

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of N-(2-hydroxy-5-phenylbenzylidene) 2,4-dimethylaniline.

also drawn for these systems to corroborate the values obtained by half-integral method. In the cases where the difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ was less than 1.78 log units, the constants were best evaluated using least square method. The second step formation constant for Pr^{3+} metal chelate could not be evaluated because of precipitation of metal ions probably due to metal ion hydrolysis.

Limits of error⁴ and the standard deviation⁵ for $\log K$ values were determined. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability constants was found to be $\text{Pr}^{3+} > \text{Nd}^{3+} > \text{Y}^{3+} > \text{Dy}^{3+} > \text{Gd}^{3+} > \text{Sm}^{3+}$.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

	$\mu = 0.1 M$						
	H^+	Y^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Sm^{3+}	Gd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}
$\log K_1$	9.83	7.10	8.43	7.94	6.22	6.64	6.73
$\log K_2$	3.33	6.11	—	6.14	5.86	6.03	6.32
Standard Deviation	± 0.01	± 0.07	± 0.05	± 0.08	± 0.06	± 0.06	± 0.07
Limits of Error	± 0.007	± 0.04	± 0.06	± 0.05	± 0.04	± 0.04	± 0.04

* For proton association H^+ , K_1 and K_2 corresponds to the species LH and LH_2^+ respectively, while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 corresponds species ML_1 and ML_2 respectively.

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